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How entrepreneurial is engineering education?

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INTRODUCTION

SEFI 2018 proclaims in its introduction “Creativity, innovation and entrepreneurship must obviously be part of any engineering educational program”. Discussing this pronouncement from an entrepreneurship education research perspective, it is questionable whether entrepreneurship *is* actually part of engineering study programs. This article aims to enrich the scientific discourse in engineering education research by contributing to specific foundations of entrepreneurship education in STEM degree programs. While politically and practically driven debates on employability or entrepreneurial activity call for advanced entrepreneurial agility at universities, the question of whether entrepreneurship is “part of any program” has not yet been exhaustively researched. Even though an international discourse on approaches to entrepreneurship education arouse in the last decades, it is usually assumed that for non-business students, especially in STEM degree programs, entrepreneurship education is rarely embedded in the curriculum. However, nobody really knows because exhaustive curriculum analysis is a bumpy road to success. Thus, our main question is: How is entrepreneurship embedded in higher education STEM degree programs?

1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

1.1 Exploring: Research in engineering and entrepreneurship education

This paper aims to bring together two research communities. First, we are looking at the development of engineering education research (EER) in the last decades [1, 2, 3]. While it is still under discussion whether EER can be described as a discipline, a community or a field [3], a lot of research on the core questions of EER topics has been conducted so far [1]. On the one side, general and broad-ranging topics are discussed, e.g. “the nature of engineering knowledge, which topics should be taught and how they should be taught, and the social and organizational contexts of engineering and engineering education” [1, p22]. On the other side, quite specific questions are addressed, such as chances and challenges of e-learning or problem-based learning, skills, diversity, recruitment, engineering educators, student learning processes [1]. Much work has been devoted to questions of curriculum development [1, 4], where aspects of embedding entrepreneurship are also discussed [5].

Second, we observe a vivid community of research in entrepreneurship education (REE) in the last decades [6]. Within this discipline (community or field), issues are discussed in a complex and heterogeneous way. To date, the terminology of entrepreneurship education is unclear [6], and heterogeneous questions are being debated. On the one side, we see general questions of the character and issues of entrepreneurship education as a research field [6]. On the other side, we see a more narrow perspective on specific questions, e.g. contrasts between a “traditional” and “entrepreneurial” way of teaching, other pedagogical approaches, effects of entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial mindsets and embedding of entrepreneurship in so called non-business disciplines curricula [6]. Within this field, most research is carried out with business students, as most entrepreneurship researchers themselves have this background and entrepreneurship is often taught to this target group. While the embedding of entrepreneurship in engineering curricula was already proclaimed as one of the hottest topics in the USA about 15 years ago [7], we are still faced with the situation that little research has been done on this question to date [8]. Reflecting this brief overview,

this paper aims to explore the specific question of the integration of entrepreneurship into engineering curricula and thus to link relevant issues of both communities.

1.2 Focusing: Core definitions

To do so, there is a need to set some core definitions in EER and REE. To explore the question “How entrepreneurial is engineering education?” we define engineering education in the context of higher education in STEM fields, known as abbreviation for science, technology, engineering and mathematics. However clear this classification may appear, it remains unclear which teaching and learning contents, fields of study or subjects are meant exactly. This paper defines STEM according to ISCED-F educational classification, published by OECD and UNESCO [9], as broad fields of education and training: natural sciences, mathematics and statistics (MS), information and communication technologies (ICT) and engineering, manufacturing and construction (ENG). Consequently, engineering education is a very broad field, being split up in six narrow fields (a) chemical engineering and processes, environmental protection technology (ENG-CH), (b) electricity and energy, electronics and automation (ENG-EL), (c) mechanics and metal trades, motor vehicles, ships and aircraft (ENG-ME), (d) manufacturing and processing (ENG-MP), (e) architecture and construction (ENG-AC), and (f) other engineering sciences including industrial engineering and management (ENG-OS).

Entrepreneurship education can be defined based on a wide or a narrow notion of entrepreneurship. Narrow definitions focus on uncovering entrepreneurial opportunities, business development, self-employment, business creation and growth, i.e. the question of how to become an entrepreneur. In contrast, broad definitions focus on aspects of personality development, creativity, initiative, action orientation, i.e. the question of how an entrepreneurial thinking and acting person can be developed [6]. In addition, the common starting point of all variations of entrepreneurship education remains the concept of value creation – and this term can be understood in a broad sense as financial, cultural or social value. The common goal of entrepreneurship education seems to be the development of entrepreneurial competences [6]. Some typologies of entrepreneurship education exist. For our research, we chose a new typology that differentiates entrepreneurship education types into traditional (TEE), creation (CEE), value creation (VaCEE), venture creation (VeCEE) and sustainable venture (SVEE) approaches [11].

1.3 Questioning: How entrepreneurial is engineering education?

The debate in EER shows that there is a discussion around the question of how to improve engineering curricula. Arguing from the perspective of REE we assume that in general the curricular anchoring of entrepreneurship education has positive effects [10]. A brief overview of the status quo of research shows that many case studies for several universities exist. For the case of Germany, we find the specific situation that associations (e.g. German Association of Engineers) explicitly advocate entrepreneurship education in higher education for engineers, but up to now, the concrete status quo of embedding entrepreneurship education in curricula is not known. To sum up: Even though the relevance of entrepreneurship education for engineering is known in research and praxis, there is no knowledge about the extent to which engineering students are confronted with contents of entrepreneurship education in Germany. Therefore, we address the question: How entrepreneurial is engineering education?

2 EMPIRICAL STUDY

2.1 Method and data description

A comprehensive document search and analysis of study course documents of all STEM study programs in six German Laender has been carried out in the period of 04/2017-12/2017. All programs have been selected from the database of the Hochschulrektorenkonferenz (German Rectors' Conference). The adjusted sample includes 1361 study programs at 58 higher education institutions. In a second step, N=2220 documents have been collected (study and examination regulations, module regulations and descriptions) and digitally stored. Those documents were searched for subjects related to entrepreneurship education using the digital search function. A positive list was used to search relevant terms such as "gründ*" or "entre*" (for founding, start-up management, entrepreneurship etc.). Finally, those course descriptions including elements of entrepreneurship education were analysed via content analysis.

The sample is almost equally distributed between study programs at universities (n=684) and study programs at universities of applied sciences (n=674). Almost exclusively, study programs are offered by public universities (n=1311). Private universities provide 4 percent of the study programs in this sample (n=50). According to degrees, the sample shows a balanced distribution of bachelor's degree programs (46 percent) and master's programs (47 percent). Allocation over six German Laender reaches from 10.4 percent (n=142 study programs) in Brandenburg to 29.2 percent (n=397 study programs) in Saxony.

2.2 Curricular anchoring referred to broad and narrow fields of study

A binary variable has been used to code whether or not a study program includes entrepreneurship. In the complete sample, 19.3 percent of study programs (n=263 out of 1361) include entrepreneurship. The ISCED-F categories allow a comparison of the broad field of ENG with the two other broad STEM fields MS and ICT. Results show (Fig.1) that 18.33 percent of engineering curricula include entrepreneurship, which is almost average. While ICT has the biggest share with 31.58 percent, study programs in the broad field of MS have the lowest share with 13.02 percent of programs including entrepreneurship

Fig. 1 – Study programs with/without entrepreneurship according to broad fields of study, numbers in percent

A detailed view on the narrow fields of ENG shows that especially study programs in the narrow fields of ENG-OS and ENG-ME include entrepreneurship above average with 27.2 and 21 percent. For the remaining narrow fields of ENG, entrepreneurship is included in 15.6 percent of the cases.

Reflecting the results from the perspective of different university types (Fig. 2), it can be observed that 21 percent of ENG study programs at universities of applied sciences include entrepreneurship while only 13.3 percent of ENG study programs at universities do so. Compared to the other broad fields, a similar observation can be made here. In both fields, the share of study programs that include entrepreneurship is higher at universities of applied sciences than at universities.

Fig. 2 Study programs with/without entrepreneurship according to university types and broad fields of study, numbers in percent

Furthermore, it can be highlighted that there is almost no difference between Bachelor and Master programs regarding the embedding of entrepreneurship. 19.9 percent of ENG study programs on bachelor level and 18.7 percent of ENG study programs on master level include entrepreneurship. It is remarkable that the German Diploma still exists in the field of ENG. Only 8.8 percent of ENG diploma study programs include entrepreneurship.

Fig. 3 Study programs with/without entrepreneurship according to degrees and broad fields of study, numbers in percent

2.3 Course analysis

In a second step, we analysed in detail the identified courses on entrepreneurship in STEM curricula. Up to six courses related to entrepreneurship were identified in one study program (Fig.4). Usually, ENG study programs include one course with content related to entrepreneurship. A maximum of four courses in one study program could be found. Compared to the other broad fields, some differences can be observed. While MS study programs include up to six courses, the common model is one course including entrepreneurship. In ICT, more study programs were identified including two (16,67 percent) or three (12,82 percent) courses.

Fig. 4 Total amount of courses related to entrepreneurship in one study program, sorted by broad fields, numbers in percent

Furthermore, the courses in all broad fields mainly have a duration of one term. 86.96 percent of entrepreneurship courses provided by ENG study programs are one term courses, 13.04 percent are two term courses. 58.71 percent of courses provided by ENG study programs are compulsory optional subjects, 38.06 percent are core subject. Compared to the broad fields of ICT and MS, in ENG the biggest amount of courses has the character of a compulsory subject (ICT – 28.42 percent compulsory subjects, MS – 15.52 percent compulsory subjects). In addition, the character of courses has been identified. Typically, entrepreneurship related courses in ENG study programs are combined lectures with seminars (59.76 percent). Compared to other broad fields, this is the biggest amount. Only 15.85 percent of entrepreneurship related courses in ENG study programs are solely lectures and 21.34 percent are solely seminars.

Finally, we analysed course descriptions of the courses related to entrepreneurship. We illustrate the results by the example of the narrow field ENG-EL (Fig.5). Out of 43 detected courses in 32 ENG-EL study programs for n=33 courses sufficient descriptions were available and analysed. The contextual relevance of entrepreneurship in these courses shows two extremes: either a complete course is dedicated to entrepreneurship education (contextual relevance 'high') (e.g. courses in which all themes and subthemes are oriented to the overarching agenda of business plan writing) or a single subtheme is oriented to entrepreneurship (contextual relevance 'low') (e.g. courses in marketing which include entrepreneurship as one topic beneath ten or twelve others). In addition, we categorized courses according to the underlying approaches of entrepreneurship education [11]. Two thirds of the courses examined show elements of the type TEE (traditional entrepreneurship education), while one third shows elements of the type CEE (creative entrepreneurship education). The other more advanced and complex approaches to entrepreneurship education (VaCEE, VeCEE and SVEE) were not identified in the course descriptions.

Fig. 5 Course analysis regarding contextual relevance and types of entrepreneurship education, subsample ENG-EL (n=33)

3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

If – as SEFI 2018 introduction proclaims - “creativity, innovation and entrepreneurship must obviously be part of any engineering educational program”, there is a lot to do for STEM study programs in Germany. Only 19.3 percent of the study programs embed entrepreneurship education in their curriculum. Looking into the details, only 50 percent of the identified courses (in our example ENG-EL) have a high contextual relevance of entrepreneurship. If we reflect on this result, entrepreneurship education does not seem to have the status of one of the “hottest topics” at engineering schools, as was the case in the USA 15 years ago [7]. For future research, we still have to understand the reasons why engineering education in Germany does not seem to be entrepreneurial. We are currently seeing these three aspects. (1) Entrepreneurship education is in the hands of the Faculties of Economic Sciences. Often enough, students in these subjects are the primary target group of their teaching. For future research, it could be a fruitful idea to investigate whether or not the institutional affiliation of the lecturers is a relevant factor for a successful integration of entrepreneurship into non-business study programs. (2) In view of the broad and narrow definitions of entrepreneurship education, interesting research questions also arise: Which peculiarities and specificities does engineering entrepreneurship education have with regard to the questions of “how an engineer becomes an entrepreneur” and “how an entrepreneurially thinking and acting engineer can be developed”. (3) Since 1998 there has been a state-aided programme in Germany with the aim of promoting entrepreneurship at universities. The permeation of university teaching is among the objectives of the program. In light of our results, the question arises as to why this goal has not yet been achieved to a greater extent. In particular, it would be important to explore how government support affects entrepreneurship education of non-business students. Taking these observations into account, we look forward to discussing our findings with the SEFI community to gain a deeper reflection of our work from an international perspective.

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